

Windfall

Developed by: Persuasive Games LLC

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Keywords

Business Ethics, City Planning, Economics, Renewable Energy, Resource Management, Strategic Decision-making, Sustainability

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Windfall* (2009). © Persuasive Games LLC. Reproduced from the official browser version of the game.

Introduction

Windfall (see Figure 1) is a browser-based Flash game developed by Persuasive Games LLC in 2009. Given the game's design and mechanics, it's reasonable to assume the target demographic is teens and young adults.

The main objective of the game is to reach a specified energy offset goal as quickly as possible by strategically building wind turbines in locations with the best wind conditions and keeping the locals in one's good graces. Simply put, the player's goal is to generate profit from sustainable energy.

Through gameplay, Persuasive Games LLC aims to show players the struggles of profitably creating sustainable energy.

Facts

Release date:	2009
Developer:	Persuasive Games LLC
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	20–40 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	Web game, accessible on a computer
Material:	None
Price:	Free

Resonance & Criticism

The concept and game mechanics of Windfall are well-established and can be seen in other resource management/city-building games, such as the "Anno" game series, where the player aims to reach a certain number of resources while staying aware of the locals' satisfaction levels.

There is no information on the contexts in which the game is predominantly used, it has not received any awards, and no published ratings or reviews from experts or players are available. The game's homepage mentions a leaderboard for its individual difficulty levels; however, I was unable to access it. Player numbers are also not available to the public.

Game Principle & Process

The educational goal of Windfall is to simulate the process of creating profitable wind farms. The player's objective is to reach a specified energy offset goal within 3 years. They can achieve this by strategically building wind turbines in areas with the best wind conditions. These places can be uncovered by researching the selected location. The player, however, has to find the right balance between the value of the land and the wind conditions offered by each turbine built. The more turbines the player builds, the more energy they can produce and get closer to their goal. To manage their resources correctly, players are rewarded with

funds, which are necessary to progress in the game. On the other hand, if the player builds turbines in the wrong spaces and lowers the land's value too much, the locals will become angry, and the player will be punished by having to give up a chunk of their monthly earnings to appease the angry residents. Therefore, the player never directly engages in any social situations; however, they have to keep the potential social consequences in mind.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The gameplay and game objectives are fairly straightforward and do not require a supervisor or an additional teacher.

The objective of showing the players the process and difficulties of creating profitable wind farms is woven through the game itself. The players have to ensure they have sufficient financial resources to expand their farms and conduct enough research to find the optimal placement for the turbines. However, they also have to remain aware and mindful of the locals.

While the game's objective is relatively straightforward, one could argue that the topic itself is subtle enough to get lost in the mechanics. In other words, when a player plays this game unquestioningly, without access to any information about it beforehand, they may perceive it as just another resource-management flash game, completely ignoring its theme of profitable clean energy.

Effectiveness

There is currently no research or empirical findings on the effectiveness of this specific game. Yet, suppose we apply Ian Bogost's rule of procedural learning from his book "Persuasive Games" (2007). In that case, Windfall's approach of teaching through interaction with systems that mimic real-world processes can be categorized as highly sustainable. This "learning by doing" approach is also viewed as a sustainable learning method by other academic publications (Pineda-Martínez et al., 2023; Janakiraman et al., 2018), especially for players who are already familiar with strategy and resource management games. It presents clear goals and gives immediate feedback, which supports player engagement. It also offers three difficulty levels, allowing players to adjust the game to their skill set. Overall, Windfall may successfully engage players who are already familiar with this genre of strategy and resource management games; yet, it may offer a less immersive experience for novices or first-time players of these genres.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The financial punishment of players could create the impression that companies and larger organizations can do as they please, as long as they have the funds to appease the angry locals. While not wholly untrue, the game's lack of dialogue and direct interaction with the town's citizens leaves this problematic aspect lacking nuance. Additionally, the game's information is

likely based on data from the time it was made (2009); therefore, some data or assumptions about profitable, sustainable energy may now be outdated.

Since Windfall is a browser-based, non-physical game, it does not pose any risk of physical injury, aside from those related to general long-term computer use.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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